

From Image to Neutrosophic Image

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In recent years, the growth of computer technology, using multimedia data in various fields such as remote sensing, medical and online information services the massive volume of electronic data a large part of which is in the form of images. Thus the need for efficient and automated search tools to index and retrieve information from these visual databases is necessary.

The image as mathematical object

- ▣ An image is mathematically represented by an $m \times n$ matrix
- ▣ $I = [g_{ij}]_{m \times n}$
- ▣ With entities $g(i, j)$ corresponding to the intensity to the given pixel located at the node (i, j)

The image in the Neutrosophic Domain

In the ND each pixel of the image is represented by three values \square

$$P_{ij} = \{T_{ij}, I_{ij}, F_{ij}\}$$

$$T(i, j) = \frac{\bar{g}(i, j) - \bar{g}_{min}}{\bar{g}_{max} - \bar{g}_{min}}$$

$$I(i, j) = \frac{\delta(i, j) - \delta_{min}}{\delta_{max} - \delta_{min}}$$

$$F(i, j) = \frac{\bar{g}_{max} - \bar{g}(i, j)}{\bar{g}_{max} - \bar{g}_{min}}$$

The image in the ND

When $\bar{g}(i, j)$ is the mean intensity in some neighborhood w of the pixel

$$\bar{g}(i, j) = \frac{1}{w \times w} \sum_{m=i-\frac{w}{2}}^{m=i+\frac{w}{2}} \sum_{n=j-\frac{w}{2}}^{n=j+\frac{w}{2}} g(m, n)$$

And

$$\delta(i, j) = \text{abs} (g(i, j) - \bar{g}(i, j))$$

Hence in the Neutrosophic Domain the image becomes A 3D matrix □

$$I_{ND} = [T_{ij} \quad I_{ij} \quad F_{ij}]$$

, With dimension(mxn3)

DIMENSION REDUCTION

In real crisp domain, there are several techniques to reduce the dimension of the desired object(image)

- MDS multidimensional scaling
- PCA principle component analysis
- LLE locally linear embedding
- ISOMAP isometric feature mapping

DIMENSION REDUCTION

The main idea is to use a distance matrix that computes the dissimilarity (similarity) between the objects (images),

To embed these objects into a subspace of lower dimension

HAUSSDORFF DISTANCE BETWEEN TWO NEUTROSOPHIC SETS

For A,B two neutrosophic sets of the universe X

$$d_H(A,B) = \max_i \{ |T_A(x_i) - T_B(x_i)|, |I_A(x_i) - I_B(x_i)|, |F_A(x_i) - F_B(x_i)| \}$$

This distance operator satisfies the following axioms

$$d_H(A,B) \geq 0$$

$$d_H(A,B) = 0 \text{ if and only if } A=B$$

$$d_H(A,B) = d_H(B,A)$$

IF $A \leq B \leq C$, A, B, C neutrosophic sets (NS), then
 $d_H(A,C) \geq d_H(A,B)$ and $d_H(A,C) \geq d_H(B,C)$

MULTIDIMENSIONAL SCALING MDS

We are using this method to embed the data specified in the dissimilarity matrix (Hausdorff distance matrix H)

Into a manifold, which is a topological space that resembles Euclidean space near the points

Here the objects are represented as points in a low dimensional space, such that the distances between the points match the observed dissimilarity as closely as possible

THE MDS TECHNIQUE

THE STARTING POINT IS TO COMPUTE A NEW MATRIX T, WHOSE ELEMENTS

$$T_{rc} = -\frac{1}{2} [H_{rc}^2 - H_{r.}^2 - \hat{H}_{.c}^2 - \hat{H}_{.o}^2]$$

Where $H_{r.}$ is the average value over the r_th row in the distance matrix H

$\hat{H}_{.c}$ is the average value over the c_th row the distance matrix H

$\hat{H}_{.o}$ is the average value over all the rows & columns of H.

THE MDS TECHNIQUE

The next step is to perform a spectral
Decomposition on T to get

$$T = \varphi \Lambda \varphi^T$$

Where Λ is a diagonal matrix with the eigen
values of T as the elements of its diagonal
and φ is the matrix which its columns are
the corresponding eigen vectors

THE MDS TECHNIQUE

Finally, the young-householder decomposition is performed on T to find a coordinates matrix X , that is $T = X^T X$

Hence, $x = \sqrt{\Lambda} \varphi^T$

where the columns of X is the coordinates vector of each point in the low dimensional space .